

Date of publication xxxx 00, 0000, date of current version xxxx 00, 0000.

Digital Object Identifier .DOI

Fingerprinting Localization based on Super Resolution CSI Features

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This work was supported a CHIST-ERA grant for project CHASER (CHIST-ERA-22-WAI-01) by Research Council of Finland grant 359837 and the SNS JU project 6GARROW under the EU's Horizon program grant 101192194.

ABSTRACT We consider fingerprint localization based on super-resolution features for single point massive multiple-input multiple-output (MIMO) systems. We consider k -nearest neighbours (k NN), weighted k -nearest neighbors (W - k NN) as well as neural network based localization. The radio environment is characterized by several multipath components. We investigate several channel state information (CSI) features. We study the localization performance when the CSI feature includes absolute delays, relative delays, and no-delay information of multipath components. Simulation results based on the DeepMIMO data-set for a challenging non line-of-sight environment show that a) treating the angle and delay separately and formulating the normalized polar feature outperforms other CSI features from the literature, b) the neural network based fingerprint localization is remarkably superior to the W - k NN based fingerprinting localization using the same features, and c) the best localization performance is obtained when absolute delay information is available. Localization accuracy with few centimeters resolution is achieved by the proposed feature and based on neural network localization, less than 30 cm average localization error can be achieved based on relative delays with the angles and powers of multipath components, and less than 60 cm average localization error can be achieved for the no-delay case (i.e., power and angle of arrival of MPCs).

INDEX TERMS Channel state information, multi-path components, super-resolution feature, fingerprint localization.

I. INTRODUCTION

Existing positioning approaches are not universally applicable: User equipments (UEs) may not have global navigation satellite system (GNSS) positioning capabilities, they may be indoors or without satellite coverage. Accurate localization is expected to be critical for future wireless systems to fully support industrial internet of things (IIoT), autonomous systems and extended reality services [1], [2].

Beyond fifth-generation (5G) mobile communication systems have several enablers such as massive multiple-input multiple-output (MIMO) technology, beamforming, huge amounts of available spectrum and small cell networks to achieve sub-meter positioning accuracy [1], [3], [4].

Recent studies on 5G-based localization show positioning accuracy below one meter by means of network-based time of arrival (ToA) and angle of arrival (AoA). However, these levels of accuracy are mainly achievable in line-of-

sight (LoS) conditions, and are difficult to reach in more challenging non-line-of-sight (NLoS) conditions [1], [2], [5]. Geometric localization method based on AoA and time difference-of-arrival (TDoA) is widely used for LoS conditions. Several iterative algorithms to reduced computation complexity are considered [6], [7]. Practical time-based positioning systems require either a clock synchronization among basestations (BSs) to utilize TDoA measurements or to adopt a two-way-ranging (TWR) scheme and then use ToA localization algorithms. In complex NLoS environments, no simple models exist. Therefore, scarce work has been done on Cramer-Rao bound analysis in NLoS environments and, for those existing ones, their models are very complicated and only for exceptional cases [8].

In [9], the authors consider multipath assisted positioning. Multipath components (MPCs) are treated as signals emitted from virtual transmitters, which are time synchronized to the

physical transmitter and static in their position. The authors show that the use of virtual transmitters to assist localization is beneficial, however the computation complexity is unavoidable.

A promising solution to achieve improved accuracy in NLoS conditions and highly cluttered multipath environments, is to use machine learning (ML) positioning. Fingerprint localization is considered as the main positioning method in 3GPP Rel-18 discussion on artificial intelligence (AI) / ML for positioning accuracy enhancement. The CSI features need to be collected at several known locations to create a database. After creating the database, model training is performed if needed. The location can be estimated directly by the k-nearest neighbour (kNN) regression, or a deep neural network [10], [11]. For example, kNN fingerprinting is widely used for this purpose [11]–[13]. The localization accuracy of kNN based fingerprinting highly depends on the used channel state information (CSI) feature and the feature distance. The simplest form of CSI feature based fingerprinting, utilizes received signal strength (RSS). Applying more generic CSI features for fingerprinting provides better localization performance than only relying on RSS [12].

Several CSI features can be considered such as angle of arrival (AoA) or time of flight (ToF), power delay profile (PDP) and channel impulse response (CIR). In [14], fingerprint localization based on channel covariance and CIR features are considered. The finite resolution feature, i.e., angle-delay matrix is proposed for fingerprint localization in [15].

In particular, the weighted k-nearest neighbour (W-kNN) is widely applied, because of its high accuracy, especially when the data set size is small, in addition to a low computational cost [13], [16], [17]. In [13], W-kNN shows better localization result than DeepNet based on a measured data set. In [13], the authors apply kNN localization based on dimensionally reduced CSI features. In [18], an algorithm to reduce the computational complexity of finding k-nearest neighbours is proposed.

To address the problem of having small data sets, channel extraction models and transfer learning frameworks are considered. For feature extraction models, the model is trained in a self-supervised manner without labeled data using several data sets. The localization head is then trained using a small data set [19]–[23].

Channel modeling studies have demonstrated that the wireless channel can be characterized by a set of few parameters, such as angle of arrival, angle of departures and delays of multipath components [24], [25]. The problem of delay estimation is a classical array signal processing problem, and methods such as MUSIC, ESPRIT, and matrix Pencil are applicable. Moreover, when measurements are collected using the antenna arrays, these methods can be extended to two-dimensional (2-D) methods for joint angle and delay estimation [7], [26], [27]. In [28], an enhanced super resolution path delay estimation method is proposed,

considering forward-backward averaging path delay matrix. In [29], a high-precision method AoA estimation is considered using CSI from a single WiFi base station, utilizing a machine learning framework.

A. RELATED WORKS

The PDP based fingerprint localization takes advantage of the entire measured PDP, i.e., the whole temporal diversity. In the case of a synchronous network, the system can use data from only a single point to determine location. For an asynchronous network, ToA information is not available. Multipoint signal reception is desirable specially in this situation: i.e., the measured PDP can determine the TDoA between different base stations (BSs) [30].

In [31], the authors consider ToA based fingerprint localization, assuming TWR, where two to four messages need to be exchanged based on the protocol. A real-world ultra-wideband dataset is considered for evaluation. In [32], the authors analyze the pairwise error probability (PEP) for the PDP fingerprint and find that it exhibits a certain diversity order, linked to the number of paths, i.e., a richer multipath environment leads to smaller PEP.

In [12], the authors consider multipath fingerprinting, taking full advantage of the finite resolution in the angle and delay domains for massive MIMO- orthogonal-frequency division-multiplexing (OFDM) systems. An angle delay channel power matrix fingerprint is extracted from instantaneous channel state information.

In [33], the ToA-AoA-RSS fingerprint localization method is considered, which consists of two phases; In phase 1, the ToA is employed for coarse localization to narrow down the fingerprint database. In phase 2, feature parameters to construct the fingerprint database together with the coarse localization coordinates obtained from the ToA are used, then a matching algorithm is utilized to determine the coordinate of the localized point.

Channel charting (CC) has recently emerged as a framework for relative localization [34]. CC consists of learning a mapping between CSI samples and points in a so-called channel chart. In [35], the super resolution angle-power feature is used for CC. In [36], the super-resolution angle-delay-power profile is considered. The super-resolution feature is represented as a point in the 2D Cartesian coordinate system. The earth-mover distance is used to measure the feature distance.

In [37], we consider the angle-delay super resolution feature for CC. We use the normalized polar form, and investigate several feature distances. The CC based of this feature leads to the state-of-the-art quality CC. In [37], we focus on feature distances, and find that combining the distances of two presentations improves the CC. Few works in the literature consider super resolution features for localization, either the AoA or delay of MPCs are considered. Furthermore, most of the works, consider several access points not only a single point.

B. CONTRIBUTIONS

In this paper, we consider fingerprint localization using super resolution features in single point (one base station) massive MIMO systems. We consider a systematic approach, where we study the effect of number of MPCs, feature representation and localization algorithm. We study the importance of the delay information of MPCs. To the best of authors' knowledge this problem have not studied in the literature. We are able to characterize the gain from using the absolute delay compared to relative delay, and the gain from using the relative delay compared to no-delay information.

The main contributions can be summarized as

- We investigate three important cases based on the availability of the delay information of MPCs: Absolute delay, relative delay and no-delay for super resolution CSI features.
- We devise a normalized polar form of the super resolution feature¹ for the three above cases and compare its performance with other representations from the literature.
- We consider W-kNN as well as Neural Networks (NNet) based fingerprint localization. We study the effect of the number of neighbours on the localization performance. For the NNet, we investigate the effect of the network structure on the localization performance.
- We investigate the effect of the number of MPCs on the localization performance of W-kNN and NNet.

C. PAPER STRUCTURE

The remainder of this paper is organized as follows: In Section II, the system model is presented. In Section III, CSI features and distance are presented. In section IV, fingerprinting localization framework is discussed. Simulation results are presented and discussed in Section V. Finally, conclusions are drawn in Section VI.

II. SYSTEM MODEL

We consider a massive MIMO base station with a uniform linear array (ULA) of A antennas. The wireless signal transmitted from a UE propagates along M multipaths.

The baseband channel response vector at the BS form multipath component l arising from an impulse transmitted at time 0 is

$$c_l = \sqrt{\alpha_l} e^{-j\beta_l} a(\theta_l) \delta(\tau_l), \quad (1)$$

where $\delta(\cdot)$ is the Dirac delta distribution, $\sqrt{\alpha_l} e^{-j\beta_l}$ is the complex attenuation, τ_l the propagation delay, and θ_l the angle-of-arrival (AoA) of path l . The array steering vector corresponding to AoA θ is

$$a(\theta) = [1, e^{-j2\pi \frac{r \sin \theta}{\lambda_c}}, \dots, e^{-j2\pi \frac{r(A-1) \sin \theta}{\lambda_c}}]^T, \quad (2)$$

where r is the antenna element spacing and λ_c is the carrier wavelength.

¹We consider normalized polar feature for CC in [37].

Considering an OFDM system with N subcarriers, assuming the cyclic prefix is larger than the maximum delay spread, the channel frequency response vector at the n th subcarrier becomes

$$h_n = \sum_{l=0}^{M-1} \sqrt{\alpha_l} e^{-j\beta_l} a(\theta_l) e^{-j2\pi n \frac{\tau_l}{NT}}, \quad (3)$$

where T is the sample interval, and M is the number of multipaths.

Channel covariance matrices are able to capture how the scattering environment is seen from the various UE locations, therefore producing smooth manifolds that preserve the local geometry of UEs [14]. The covariance matrix is computed as $\mathbf{R} = \mathbb{E}[\mathbf{h}\mathbf{h}^H]$, where \mathbb{E} is the expectation operator.

III. CSI FEATURES AND DISTANCES

For fingerprinting based localization, several CSI features have been considered such as CSI frequency response, covariance matrix, and finite resolution angle-delay matrix [11], [12], [12]–[14]. The selection of the CSI feature as well as the feature distance highly affects the resulting performance.

In this paper, we consider super-resolution features. Based on the availability of the delay information, we investigate three scenarios; absolute delay, relative delay and no delay. Obtaining absolute delay information requires either to have a synchronized system, where all UEs and BSs use the same clock, or to have a two way ranging system as is assumed in [31] and discussed for 5G NR based positioning systems [3]. To get a relative delay does not require that all UEs have the same clock, which is more practical. The first detected MPC is assumed at zero delay and the delays of remaining MPCs are measured with respect to this reference. For the "no delay" case, only the power and angle information are assumed available. In general, the angle-power information of MPCs, does not require to have a system with large bandwidth. It is worth to model and study the effect of environmental dynamics on localization performance using super resolution features in future work.

The estimation of the super resolution features from the CSI matrix is out scope of this paper, for more details see [25], [38].

It is not straightforward to measure the distance between two super-resolution CSI features. Different orderings of the MPCs may result in different distances, and handling two features with different number of MPCs is not trivial. First, we will discuss the super resolution representations from the literature. Second, will discuss the Polar Normalized feature based on the available delay information. Third, we will discuss CSI feature distances.

A. BENCHMARK REPRESENTATIONS

We summarize the super resolution representations from the literature as follows:

FIGURE 1: Two nearby UEs; the received signals at the BS are with the same angle, but with but with large delay difference.

- The Angle-Power Feature (APF) is given as [35]:

$$\mathbf{f}_{\text{APF}}^{i,l} = \begin{bmatrix} p_{i,l}^{-1/\nu} \cos(\theta_{i,l}) \\ p_{i,l}^{-1/\nu} \sin(\theta_{i,l}) \end{bmatrix}, \quad (4)$$

where $p_{i,l}$ is the power of l 'th MPC of UE i and ν is the path-loss exponent. This feature was used to cluster MPCs.

- The Super-resolution Rectangular Feature (SRF) is given as [?]:²

$$\mathbf{f}_{\text{SRF}}^{i,l} = \begin{bmatrix} \tau_{i,l} \cos(\theta_{i,l}) \\ \tau_{i,l} \sin(\theta_{i,l}) \end{bmatrix}. \quad (5)$$

This feature is used with the earth mover distance to create a dissimilarity matrix for CC in [?].

- The Multi-Path Separation (MPS) feature of multipath component l of UE i is [39], [40]

$$\mathbf{f}_{\text{MPS}}^{i,l} = \begin{bmatrix} \cos(\theta_{i,l}) \\ \sin(\theta_{i,l}) \\ \zeta \tau_{i,l} / \tau_{\max} \end{bmatrix}, \quad (6)$$

where $\theta_{i,l}$, and $\tau_{i,l}$ are the AoA and delay of l th MPC of UE i , τ_{\max} is the maximum delay and ζ is a weight. This feature is used to cluster MPCs.

B. MOTIVATION FOR POLAR FEATURE

The Super-resolution Rectangular Feature maps the angle and delay of a MPC to 2D point in the space. This model couples the delay and AoA, i.e., a nearby point needs to have a small change in both the AoA and delay. Figure 1 illustrates a scenario of two UEs transmitting from nearby physical locations. The received signal at the BS from each UE has one MPC. The propagation delay of the green UE is much larger than the propagation delay of the red UE,

as shown by the length of green dashed line compared to length of red dashed line. There is no angular difference between the received signals from the two UEs at the BS. If the super rectangular features of the two UEs are used with the Euclidean distance, a large distance is obtained. To handle such challenging scenarios, we treat the angle and delay separately.

Furthermore, the polar feature can be used with the relative delay case without losing the angle of the first multipath component as we will discuss next. Providing a mathematical derivation and justification for the superiority of the polar feature is currently an open question, due to the complexity of the problem.

C. CSI FEATURE REPRESENTATION

We consider the following cases based on the delay information availability.

1) Absolute Delay

We consider the "Normalized Polar Feature (NPF)" expressed as:

$$f_{\text{NPF}}^{i,l} = \begin{bmatrix} \theta_{i,l} / a_{\theta} \\ \tau_{i,l} / a_{\tau} \end{bmatrix}, \quad (7)$$

where the normalization factors $a_{\theta} = \max_{i,l} |\theta_{i,l}|$, and $a_{\tau} = \max_{i,l} \tau_{i,l}$. The normalization factors are proposed to handle different scales of the AoA and delay. This feature can be extended to handle the power of MPC l .

2) Relative Delay

We propose the normalized feature vectors with and without power as $f_{\text{RNPF}}^{i,l}$ and $f_{\text{RNPFp}}^{i,l}$, respectively, as follows:

$$f_{\text{RNPF}}^{i,l} = \begin{bmatrix} (\tau_{i,l} - \tau_{i,1}) / a_{\tau} \\ \theta_{i,l} / a_{\theta} \end{bmatrix}, \quad (8)$$

and

$$f_{\text{RNPFp}}^{i,l} = \begin{bmatrix} (\tau_{i,l} - \tau_{i,1}) / a_{\tau} \\ \theta_{i,l} / a_{\theta} \\ p_{i,l} / a_{\text{pow}} \end{bmatrix}, \quad (9)$$

where the normalization factors $a_{\text{pow}} = \max_{i,l} p_{i,l}$ and

$$a_{\tau} = \max_{i,l} (\tau_{i,l} - \tau_{i,1}),$$

$\tau_{i,1}$ is the absolute delay of the first MPC. It is worth to mention that with the normalized polar feature, the angle of first multipath component is preserved. In the contrary, if the Super-resolution Rectangular Feature (5) is used with the relative delay, it does not preserve the angle of first multipath component.

3) No Delay

We define the normalized power angle feature of multipath component l as

$$f_{\text{nPAF}}^{i,l} = \begin{bmatrix} \theta_{i,l} / a_{\theta} \\ p_{i,l} / a_{\text{pow}} \end{bmatrix}. \quad (10)$$

²Also known as the 2D Cartesian coordinate super resolution feature.

The normalization factors a_θ and a_{pow} are as in (9).

D. CSI FEATURE DISTANCE

For measuring the CSI feature distance (in input space), we have many different choices, two of which are as follows:

- 1) Using the minimum pairwise distance between two sets. In this case, all MPCs are not stacked into one vector, but instead, each MPC is represented by a separate vector. Then the Euclidean distance is used to measure the distance between two features, each belongs to one set. So, the distance of the NPF of UE i and UE j is computed as:

$$d_{\text{NPF}}^{i,j} = \min_{l',l} d(f_{\text{NPF}}^{i,l}, f_{\text{NPF}}^{j,l'}), \quad (11)$$

where $d(f_{\text{NPF}}^{i,l}, f_{\text{NPF}}^{j,l'}) = \|f_{\text{NPF}}^{i,l} - f_{\text{NPF}}^{j,l'}\|_2$, $l \in \{1, \dots, M_i\}$ and $l' \in \{1, \dots, M_j\}$ with M_i is the number of multipath components of UE i and M_j is the number of multipath components of UE j . Other feature representations will be treated similarly, i.e., in order to compute the distance for a given feature between UE i and j , we replace the NPF feature with the given feature and use (11).

In [37], the combined distance from two representations is considered. In [?], the earth mover distance (EMD) is used to compute the distance between two sets of MPCs, to obtain EMD a linear programming needs to be solved.

- 2) Stacking all MPCs in a vector and then using the Euclidean distance. The stacked feature vectors for UE i and UE j in the NPF case, denoted as x_{NPF}^i and x_{NPF}^j respectively, are given as

$$x_{\text{NPF}}^i = \begin{bmatrix} f_{\text{NPF}}^{i,1} \\ \vdots \\ f_{\text{NPF}}^{i,M} \end{bmatrix}, \quad (12)$$

and

$$x_{\text{NPF}}^j = \begin{bmatrix} f_{\text{NPF}}^{j,1} \\ \vdots \\ f_{\text{NPF}}^{j,M} \end{bmatrix}, \quad (13)$$

respectively. Missing or unavailable MPCs are filled by zeros in the corresponding entries in the stacked vector so that all vectors have the same dimension, i.e., $M = \max(M_i, M_j)$. So, the distance between the UE i and UE j in the input (feature) space is computed as

$$d_{\text{NPF}}^{i,j} = d(x_{\text{NPF}}^i, x_{\text{NPF}}^j). \quad (14)$$

In this paper, because we focus on the task of mapping from L_f -dimensional stacked-MPC vector space (i.e. feature space) to 2-dimensional location space (real coordinates of UEs) for both the NNet and the kNN cases, we use

the distance in (14) in input space for the sake of a fair comparison between the NNet and the KNN / W-kNN.

IV. FINGERPRINTING LOCALIZATION

We consider a network-based localization framework. The UE measures the CSI from a BS and reports to the network³ then, the super resolution features are extracted at the network side. In the offline phase, the network creates and saves a database, where the fingerprint is the super resolution feature for the physical location.

In the online phase, a UE measures a new CSI feature and transmits to the BS. Then the network estimates the super resolution fingerprint and uses it to estimate the location based on the available dataset. To estimate the location of a new fingerprint in the online phase, kNN, W-kNN or NNet localization can be used.

A. WEIGHTED K-NEAREST NEIGHBOR REGRESSION

The k-Nearest Neighbor (kNN) method is a simple yet effective algorithm used for fingerprinting localization. The fundamental principle behind kNN is to identify the k -closest reference points in a look-up table of fingerprints that most resemble the fingerprint of the target location.

- 1) Fingerprint Collection: Collect signal fingerprints at known locations to build a reference database (i.e., look-up table). Each fingerprint includes chosen feature vectors like NPF, SRF and APF.
- 2) Distance Calculation: For a given unknown location, measure the fingerprint and compute the distance between this fingerprint and each fingerprint in the look-up table using (14).
- 3) Neighbor Selection: Identify the k reference points with the smallest distances to the unknown fingerprint.
- 4) Location Estimation: Estimate the position of the unknown location by averaging the coordinates of the k nearest neighbors.

The kNN method's performance depends on the value of k and the choice of distance metric. A small k may lead to noisy estimates, while a large k might smooth out important local variations in the signature space.

The Weighted k-Nearest Neighbor (W-kNN) method is an extension of the kNN approach that tries to improve localization accuracy by assigning weights to the k nearest neighbors based on their distance to the target fingerprint. The rationale is that closer neighbors should have a greater influence on the estimated location than those further away. The W-kNN method follows the same steps as the kNN method, with the addition of a weighting mechanism in the location estimation step:

- 1) Weight Calculation: Assign a weight to each of the k nearest neighbors based on their distance to the target fingerprint. Common weighting functions include the inverse distance, exponential and Gaussian functions.

³Another alternative can be used, in which the BS measures the CSI from uplink transmission of a UE.

For instance, an inverse distance weight for the i -th neighbor can be calculated as:

$$\omega_i = \frac{1}{d_i + \varepsilon},$$

where d_i is the distance of the i -th neighbor and ε is a small constant to prevent division by zero.

- 2) Weighted Location Estimation: Estimate the unknown location by computing a weighted average of the coordinates of the k nearest neighbors. The estimated location $\hat{\mathbf{p}}$ can be expressed as:

$$\hat{\mathbf{p}} = \frac{\sum_{i=1}^k \omega_i \mathbf{p}_i}{\sum_{i=1}^k \omega_i},$$

where \mathbf{p}_i is the location of the i -th neighbor.

B. NEURAL NETWORKS FOR FINGERPRINTING LOCALIZATION

Neural Networks have been effectively utilized for fingerprinting localization due to their ability to model complex and non-linear relationships in feature space. Feedforward Neural Networks (NNet) are often employed to map signal strengths to coordinates, improving accuracy over traditional methods. Convolutional Neural Networks (CNNs) capture spatial dependencies in signal patterns, and Recurrent Neural Networks (RNNs), including Long Short-Term Memory (LSTM) networks, handle temporal changes in dynamic environments. In this paper, we design a single-hidden layer feedforward Neural Network (NNet) with hyperbolic tangent sigmoid activation function. The mean squared error (MSE) is considered as the loss function.

C. COMPUTATIONAL COMPLEXITY ANALYSIS

We consider the computational complexity of the online phase. Because in digital arithmetic, an addition requires an order of magnitude less operations than a multiplication, we ignore the addition process. In n -digit computation, the complexity of an addition operation is $\mathcal{O}(n)$ and a multiplication is $\mathcal{O}(n^2)$ [41]. Assuming the multiplication complexity has constant time $\mathcal{O}(1)$.

As far as the W-kNN is concerned, the heaviest computational burden is to calculate the feature distances when determining the nearest neighbors for each data vector. If the Euclidean distance in (14) is used, then the computational complexity is obtained as

$$C(L_f, L_d) = \mathcal{O}(L_f L_d), \quad (15)$$

where L_f and L_d is the length of the feature vector, and the size of data set, respectively.

On the other hand, the proposed NNet is fully connected and has only one hidden layer. Each neuron in the hidden layer calculates the inner product of the feature vector and neuron's weight vector, which is fed to the hyperbolic tangent sigmoid function. Each neuron in the output layer sums the weighted outputs of the hidden layer. Therefore the number of multiplications is a function of the number

TABLE 1: Simulation Parameters

Parameter	Value	Parameter	Value
Freq.	3.5 GHz	Subcarriers	4086
Scenario	O1-3p5	BW	100 MHz
BS Loc.	[287.5, 489.5] m	UE Loc.	Vert. str.
BS Height	6	UE Height	2 m
BS Array	32 ULA	UE Array	1

FIGURE 2: Simulation layout. The selected street segment is in pink colour. Two BSs are indicated by a red and blue stars.

of neurons in the hidden layer and output layer. Output layer has 2 neurons.

$$C(L_f, L_h) = \mathcal{O}(L_f L_h + 2L_h), \quad (16)$$

where L_h is the number of neurons in the hidden layer. From (15) and (16), note that $L_d \gg L_h$, i.e., the number of neurons in the hidden layer is much less than the number of data vectors in the lookup table. This implies that the computational burden is less in the NNet than that of the W-kNN.

V. SIMULATIONS RESULTS

A. SIMULATION SETTINGS

We use the DeepMIMO data set to generate the CSI [42]. Channels are constructed based on ray-tracing data obtained from the Remcom Wireless InSite [43] channel emulator.

Figure 2 shows the simulation layout. We consider one BS marked with red star in the layout. The UEs are located in the southern part of the vertical street. The streets have buildings on both sides. Buildings are $60\text{ m} \times 60\text{ m}$ or $60\text{ m} \times 30\text{ m}$, with the height written on the layout. A distance of 1.2 m between adjacent UEs samples is considered. Table 1 summarizes the simulation parameters. For the red BS, some locations in the street are blocked. The

data set consists of 4105 UE locations for the red marked BS, after filtering out the blocked locations. Training data set (for kNN and NNet) consists of those locations whose indices are odd. The even-index UE locations are reserved for testing (generalization performance). This yields 2053 and 2052 different UE locations for training and testing (generalization), respectively.

As seen from the simulation layout in Figure 2, with respect to BS 4 (red star) many locations in the selected street are in NLoS condition.

Taking the arguments presented in Section III into account, we consider simulations for the following scenarios:

- 1) Covariance matrix CSI feature.
- 2) Absolute delay case.
- 3) Relative-delay case without power feature.
- 4) Relative-delay case with power feature.
- 5) No delay case, i.e., angle and power features.

In our simulations, we address the following questions:

- What is the range of distance errors for the absolute delay case, relative-delay cases with and without power feature, and no delay case (i.e., angle and power features)? (Table 6)
- What is the best CSI feature vector representation for the absolute delay case? (subsection V-D)
- How many neurons should be used in the NNet architecture for the absolute delay case (subsection V-E) and for the relative delay case (subsection V-J)?
- What is the number of MPCs for the best NNet in the absolute delay case (subsection V-F) and for the relative delay case (subsection V-K)?
- How many nearest neighbors should we use for the kNN and W-kNN methods in the absolute delay case (subsection V-H) and for the relative delay case (subsection V-L)?
- What is the best CSI feature vector for no delay case? (subsection V-M)

We evaluate the localization performance in terms of average error, 80% percentile error, and the cumulative distribution function (CDF) of the error.

B. DEEP NNET FOR FINGERPRINTING LOCALIZATION

The proposed Deep Neural Network (DNNet) is based on Convolutional Neural Network (CNN) where input is treated as an "image". The input "image" is

- either the covariance matrix itself or (some of) its eigenvectors.
- either in rectangular form or in polar form
- either 1-channel or 2-channel image.

These yield 8 different Deep NNet, which are listed in Table 3.

For the 2-channel NNet:

- If the complex number is in rectangular form, then channel 1 and 2 is real and imaginary part, respectively.
- If the complex number is in polar form, then channel 1 and 2 is magnitude and phase, respectively.

TABLE 2: Abbreviations of the Methods used in Simulated Scenarios

Abbreviation	Definition
NPF	Normalized Polar Feature
SRF	Super-resolution Rectangular Feature
MPS	Multi-Path Separation
APF	Angle-Power Rectangular Feature
RNPF	Relative Delay for NPF without Power
RNPFp	Relative Delay for NPF with Power
nPAF	normalized Power Angle Feature
kNN	kNN (k-Nearest Neighbor) method - generalization
W-kNN	Weighted-k-Nearest Neighbor average - generalization
(R)kNN	kNN method with Relative Delays - generalization
(R)W-kNN	Weighted-kNN with Relative Delays - generalization
NNet-t	Neural Network - training
NNet-g	Neural Network - generalization
(R)NNet-t	Neural Network with Relative Delays - training
(R)NNet-g	Neural Network with Relative Delays - generalization

For the 1-channel NNet, channel 2 is eliminated by simply concatenating it to channel 1 matrix. The proposed DNNet architecture includes convolution, normalization, activation, pooling, self-attention, and fully connected layers, and is summarized below:

- **Input Layer:** Accepts 2D data.
- **Convolutional Layers:** Two convolutional layers extract features, with 32 filters of size 3x3 in the first layer and 64 filters of size 3x3 in the second, both employing 'same' padding to preserve spatial dimensions.
- **Batch Normalization and Activation:** Each convolutional layer is followed by batch normalization and a ReLU activation to enhance training stability and non-linearity.
- **Pooling Layers:** Max pooling with a 2x2 window and stride reduces spatial dimensions after each convolutional block.
- **Flattening:** Converts 2D feature maps into a 1D vector for subsequent processing.
- **Self-Attention Layer:** Integrates an 8-head self-attention mechanism with 64 channels to capture long-range dependencies across the features.
- **Output Layer:** A fully connected layer produces a single real-valued output, suitable for regression tasks, followed by a regression loss layer.

The number of filters, attention heads, and layers are adjusted to give the best results.

From the results in Table 3 we conclude that when the data set is small, few thousands of samples, and the feature

FIGURE 3: Deep NNet architecture for fingerprinting localization.

TABLE 3: MSE Results for Various Deep Neural Networks Designs and W-kNN for Covariance Feature

DeepNNet Design	Tr. Error [m]	Test Error [m]
Polar - Cov. Eigvecs - 1D	13.46	17.71
Polar - CovEigvecs - 2D	3.92	19.33
Polar - CovMat - 1D	15.06	16.49
Polar - CovMat - 2D	24.39	24.55
Rectangular - CovEigvecs - 1D	20.13	26.90
Rectangular - CovEigvecs - 2D	5.36	16.09
Rectangular - CovMat - 1D	17.51	17.76
Rectangular - CovMat - 2D	16.03	16.35
W-KNN (k=5), Euclidean	-	3.50

size is large 32×32 dimensions for example for covariance feature, it is not possible to have a good accuracy. In this case, using W-kNN gives better results, which can be seen in the last row of Table 3. In what follows, we investigate the shallow NNet for various super resolution CSI features.

C. SHALLOW NNET ARCHITECTURE

As an alternative to the DNNet whose input is covariance matrix or its eigenvalues, we present a shallow NNet whose input is our proposed CSI features in Section III. The shallow NNet architecture is shown in Figure 4. It has 3 layers: Input layer, single hidden layer and output layer. Input layer is simply the feature vector. The hidden layer includes the neurons which have the hyperbolic tangent sigmoid function. The output layer has 2 neurons, and those neurons do not have any nonlinear function. In Figure 4, w and b are generic representations of layer-specific and neuron-specific weight vector and scalar bias, respectively. The weight vector w represents how the neurons of in the previous layer affect the neurons in the corresponding layer in the feedforward network.

Because we have two features for each MPC for the NPF case, the input layer dimension of the NNet is 6 for 3 MPCs

FIGURE 4: The proposed feedforward NNet with 6-dimensional input vector (for 3 MPCs) and with 100 neurons in the hidden layer. The output layer has 2 neurons.

in Figure 4. On the other hand, in the RNPF case, the input layer dimension is 5. So, the input vector to the NNet in the NPF absolute delay case and the RNPF relative delay case for UE i with 3 MPCs, represented by x_{NPF}^i and x_{RNPF}^i respectively, is as follows:

$$x_{\text{NPF}}^i = \begin{bmatrix} \tau_{i,1}/a_\tau \\ \theta_{i,1}/a_\theta \\ \tau_{i,2}/a_\tau \\ \theta_{i,2}/a_\theta \\ \tau_{i,3}/a_\tau \\ \theta_{i,3}/a_\theta \end{bmatrix} \text{ and } x_{\text{RNPF}}^i = \begin{bmatrix} \theta_{i,1}/a_\theta \\ (\tau_{i,2} - \tau_{i,1})/a_\tau \\ \theta_{i,2}/a_\theta \\ (\tau_{i,3} - \tau_{i,1})/a_\tau \\ \theta_{i,3}/a_\theta \end{bmatrix}. \quad (17)$$

The cost function used for training the NNet (i.e., for determining the optimum weights w and biases b), is the

FIGURE 5: Evolution of the MSE with respect to epochs for training, validation and test datasets in the absolute delay case.

FIGURE 6: the NNnet outputs with respect to the target outputs for training, validation, test datasets as well as for all datasets combined in the absolute delay case in Figure 5

standard Mean Squared Error (MSE) function. In order to give an insight into the training, validation and test process, we show how the MSE evolves with respect to epochs in Figure 5 for the absolute delay case. As seen from the figure, the MSE is exponentially decreased in the first 10 epochs already after which the MSE continue decreasing gradually for all training, validation and test datasets. Furthermore, Figure 6 shows the NNnet outputs with respect to the target outputs for training, validation, test datasets as well as all datasets combined. Figure 6 confirms the perfect match between the target output and the corresponding NNnet output for the absolute delay case.

D. DETERMINING THE BEST CSI FEATURE

We consider the following benchmark features: The Super-resolution Rectangular Feature (SRF) [?], given in (5), Angle-Power Feature (APF) [35], given in (4) and our proposed "Normalized Polar Feature (NPF)" [37], given in (7).

The "Multi-Path Separation (MPS) feature" is not considered, because our results in [37] showed that NPF outperforms this feature.

In this subsection, we focus on the following question: What is the best feature which gives the minimum average distance error? Figure 8 shows the results for the above-mentioned feature vectors using the same NNnet architecture. The results indicate that the proposed NPF outperforms the other features.

E. DETERMINING THE NUMBER OF NEURONS FOR NNnet

In this subsection, we investigate the effect of varying the number of neurons in the NNnet architecture on the distance error performance. As depicted in Figure 9, increasing the number of neurons from 100 to 150 does not improve the error performance, which implies that the NNnet with 100 neurons offers the best trade-off between performance and computational complexity.

F. DETERMINING THE NUMBER OF MPCs

In order to determine the optimum number of MPCs, we evaluate its impact on the distance error for the NNnet, and the W-kNN methods. The CDF of the NNnet generalization error for different number of MPCs and the CDF of the average-kNN generalization error and average errors are shown in Figure 10. The figure suggests that i) the optimal number of MPCs is two for the NNnet. ii) Increasing the number of MPCs from 2 or 3 does not improve the performance of the W-kNN. It is worth to mention that UEs in the dataset do not have the same number of MPCs. A UE can have 1-8 MPCs. We consider up to 4 MPCs, selected based on the power of MPCs.

G. EFFECT OF NOISE ON THE PERFORMANCE

We consider the effect of the noise / estimation error of delay of MPCs on localization performance. The delay error is modeled by a uniformly distributed random variable in the interval $[0, D]$, where D is 10% of the maximum delay value (in our dataset, the maximum delay is $1.57 \mu\text{s}$). Accordingly, the noise has a mean of $D/2$, and variance of $\frac{D^2}{12}$. The performance results with and without noise are summarized in Table 5. The results show that the noise deteriorates the performance of all methods as expected, yet, the proposed shallow NN based on our "super features" outperforms the other methods in noise case also.

TABLE4: Simulation parameters for the scenarios in subsections.

Subsection	Delay	Feature	Number of MPC	Number of Neuron	k for W-kNN
V-D	Absolute	NPF, SRF, APF	2	100	3
V-E	Absolute	NPF	3	50 to 200	3
V-F	Absolute	NPF	1, 2, 3, 4	100	3
V-H	Absolute	NPF	3	100	3, 5, 10
V-I	Relative	RNPF, RNPFp	2, 3, 4	200	3
V-J	Relative	RNPFp	2	100 to 300	3
V-K	Relative	RNPFp	2, 3, 4	200	3
V-L	Relative	RNPFp	2	200	3, 5, 10
V-M	No delay	APF, nPAF	2, 3	100, 200	3

TABLE5: MSE results with and without noise

Method	MSE W/o noise	MSE W. noise
kNN	1.16	10.86
W-kNN	1.22	9.28
NNet-training	0.011	4.30
NNet-test	0.015	9.00

H. DETERMINING THE NUMBER OF NEAREST NEIGHBORS FOR W-KNN

In this part, we analyze the localization performance of the kNN and the W-kNN methods by varying the number of nearest neighbors k . Figure 11 presents the simulation results for different number of neighbors, which suggests that using $k = 3$ nearest neighbors provides an optimal balance between accuracy and computational complexity. While $k = 3$ and $k = 5$ nearest neighbors give comparable performance for both kNN and W-kNN, using $k = 10$ nearest neighbors deteriorates their performance.

Figure 11 also show that the NNet method is remarkably superior than both kNN and W-kNN methods in the absolute delay case using the proposed feature.

Above, we examined the fingerprinting localization performance using the proposed super resolution CSI features for various methods for the Absolute Delay case. In what follows, we investigate their performance for the Relative Delay case. In the Relative Delay case, the first delay is simply eliminated by subtracting it from the delays of the following MPCs. In other words, the second and higher delays are calculated relative to the first delay. Because

of the elimination of the 1st delay, we loose a valuable information. The question we address in the following subsections is as follows: Do the NNet, kNN and W-kNN methods in the Relative Delay case give satisfactory results despite the lost information or not?

I. RELATIVE DELAY CASE AND EXAMINING THE EFFECT OF POWER FEATURE

First, we investigate the performance of the feature vectors with and without power feature for the relative delay case. In other words, we examine the effect of including the power into the feature vector on the performance of the NNet, kNN and W-kNN methods.

The results are presented in Figure 12 for the Relative Delay case, where, for example, "RNPF-3M" represents the proposed Delay-Angle feature vector without power and with 3 MPCs and "RNPFp-4M" represents the feature vector with power for 4 MPCs. Figure 12 shows that including the normalized power feature to the feature vector remarkably improves the performance of all methods NNet, kNN and W-kNN and for different number of MPCs.

J. RELATIVE DELAY CASE AND DETERMINING THE NUMBER OF NEURONS FOR NNET

Second, we investigate the effect of varying the number of neurons in the NNet architecture for the Relative Delay case. The results for different number of neurons are presented in Figure 13 which shows that the NNet with 200 neurons offers the best trade-off between performance and computational complexity for the Relative Delay case.

Furthermore, comparing Figure 9 and Figure 13, we conclude that i) the NNet with Absolute Delay (without power feature) gives remarkably superior performance than

the NNet with Relative Delay (with power feature) using the proposed features. This is somehow expected result due to losing information when eliminating the first delay and using only the relative delay for the higher MPCs.

K. RELATIVE DELAY CASE AND DETERMINING THE NUMBER OF MPCs

In what follows, we address the following question: What is the optimum number of MPCs which minimizes the distance error for the Relative Delay case? The simulation results are shown in Figure 14, which suggests that the optimal number of MPCs is 2 for the NNet and is 3 or 4 for both kNN and W-kNN. Figure 14 also shows that the error for the kNN and W-kNN is about 1.5 meters using 3 or 4 MPCs, which is considered unacceptable if the target average localization error is about 30 cm.

L. RELATIVE DELAY CASE, DETERMINING THE NUMBER OF NEAREST NEIGHBORS FOR W-KNN

In this subsection, we address the following question: As far as the kNN and the W-kNN are concerned, how many nearest neighbors should be taken into calculation for the Relative Delay case?

Figure 15 presents the CDF of error, the average distance error and 80th percentile of the error for different number of neighbors in the W-kNN. These results suggest that 3 or 5 nearest neighbors give relatively good average error and taking 10 nearest neighbors deteriorates the performance for the layout in Figure 2.

M. NO DELAY CASE, NORMALIZED POWER-ANGLE FEATURE

Here we investigate how the choice of feature vector, number of MPCs and number of neurons affect the error performance for the no-delay case. We consider the Angle Power Feature (APF) given in (4) and the Normalized Power-Angle Feature (nPAF) given in (10). As seen from the results in lines 37 to 42 in Table 7, the APF is far from giving acceptable error performance. On the other hand, using the nPAF and NNet with 200 neurons gives an average error less than half meter (line 49, Table 7).

N. SUMMARY OF THE SIMULATION RESULTS

The average error for all simulation parameters in Table 4 are presented in Table 6 and 7. As a summary, the best average error for each category listed on p.5 are presented in Table 8. The CDFs of the errors of the best result for each category are given in Fig. 7, which clearly shows that the absolute delay case is superior to other cases.

The simulation results presented in this section yield many novel results some of which are as follows:

- Treating the angle and delay separately and formulating the normalized polar feature (NPF) outperforms other CSI features from the literature addressing the fingerprint localization problem.

FIGURE 7: The CDFs of the errors for the best result for each category in Table 8.

- The NNet based fingerprint localization is remarkably superior to the kNN and W-kNN based fingerprinting localization using the same features for the absolute delay case.
- The NNet with Absolute Delay (without power feature) gives superior performance than the NNet with Relative Delay (with power feature) using the proposed features.
- One-hidden-layer NNet with only 100 and 200 neurons would be enough to address the fingerprinting problem for the challenging NLoS scenario in Absolute-Delay and Relative Delay cases, respectively.
- Using only the first two MPCs seems to be enough for the NNet based fingerprinting for both absolute delay and relative delay cases.
- The performance of the NNet depends not only on the feature selection but also on the available delay information (absolute/relative delay). While the NNet architecture greatly outperforms the kNN and W-kNN methods for the NPF and SRF in the absolute delay case using 2 MPCs, this does not hold for the APF case (line 1 to 7 in Table 6), where both the NNet and W-kNN give unacceptable error performance.
- As far as the W-kNN based methods are concerned, taking only 3 to 5 nearest neighbors generally gives the best W-kNN performance. Increasing the number of neighbors to 10 or more generally deteriorates performance.
- In the no-delay case, the choice of the feature vector greatly affects the error performance. While the APF gives unacceptable results for any NNet structure (lines 37 to 42 in Table 7), the nPAF can give an average error less than half meter (line 49, Table 7) using the NNet with 200 neurons.

TABLE 6: Mean errors for the simulation parameters in Table 4.

Row Number	Delay	Feature	No. Neuron	No. MPCs	k	NNet-t	NNet-g	kNN	W-kNN
1	Absolute delay	APF	100	1	3	12.01	12.33	1.91	1.91
2	"	"	"	2	"	8.79	10.13	2.8	2.83
3	"	"	"	3	"	7.77	8.23	2.78	2.82
4	"	"	"	4	"	12.9	13.01	3.25	3.29
6	"	"	200	2	"	9.39	10.05	2.8	2.83
7	"	"	"	3	"	8.23	9.02	2.78	2.82
8	"	SRF	100	2	"	0.09	0.09	0.74	0.74
9	"	"	200	"	"	0.01	0.01	0.74	0.74
10	"	"	"	3	"	0.06	0.08	0.81	0.83
11	"	"	250	"	"	0.08	0.15	0.74	0.74
12	"	NPF	100	2	"	0.01	0.02	0.75	0.76
13	"	"	"	2	5	0.01	0.02	0.83	0.81
14	"	"	"	2	10	0.01	0.02	1.16	1.22
15	"	"	200	2	3	0.01	0.01	0.75	0.76
16	"	"	"	3	"	0.04	0.07	0.8	0.81
17	"	"	250	2	"	0.06	0.13	0.75	0.76
18	Relative delay (no power)	RNPF	100	2	3	7.04	7.11	7.39	6.50
19	"	"	"	3	3	7.56	7.66	7.44	6.55
20	"	"	"	4	"	8.12	8.31	7.51	6.62
21	"	"	125	2	"	6.99	7.06	7.39	6.50
22	"	"	"	"	10	6.99	7.06	7.05	6.66
23	"	"	"	3	3	7.08	7.14	7.44	6.55
24	"	"	200	2	"	6.72	6.77	7.39	6.50
25	"	"	"	3	"	6.80	6.92	7.44	6.55
26	"	"	"	4	"	6.87	7.08	7.51	6.62
27	"	"	300	2	10	6.78	6.92	7.05	6.66
28	Relative delay(with power)	RNPFp	100	2	3	1.40	1.49	1.98	2.31
29	"	"	"	3	"	2.51	2.52	1.44	1.52
30	"	"	"	4	"	3.58	3.74	1.5	1.54
31	"	"	125	2	"	0.23	0.29	1.25	1.29
32	"	"	"	"	10	0.23	0.29	1.89	2.02
33	"	"	200	"	3	0.45	0.59	1.98	2.31
34	"	"	"	"	5	0.45	0.59	1.29	1.35
35	"	"	"	"	10	0.45	0.59	1.89	2.02
36	"	"	"	3	"	2.96	2.96	1.94	2.07

TABLE7: Mean errors for the simulation parameters in Table 4 (cont.).

Row Number	Delay	Feature	No. Neuron	No. MPCs	k	NNet-t	NNet-g	kNN	W-kNN
37	No delay	APF	100	1	3	12.01	12.33	1.91	1.91
38	"	"	"	2	"	8.79	10.13	2.8	2.83
39	"	"	"	3	"	7.77	8.23	2.78	2.82
40	"	"	200	1	"	11.84	11.99	1.91	1.91
41	"	"	"	2	"	9.39	10.05	2.8	2.83
42	"	"	"	3	"	8.23	9.02	2.78	2.82
43	"	nPAF	100	1	"	0.79	1.12	1.81	1.84
44	"	"	"	2	"	1.05	1.11	1.58	1.62
45	"	"	"	3	"	4.22	4.21	1.45	1.49
46	"	"	"	2	10	1.05	1.11	2.26	2.41
47	"	"	125	2	3	0.97	1.02	1.58	1.62
48	"	"	200	1	"	1.62	1.85	1.81	1.84
49	"	"	"	2	"	0.43	0.56	1.58	1.62
50	"	"	"	2	10	0.43	0.56	2.26	2.41
51	"	"	"	3	3	1.91	2.00	1.45	1.49

TABLE8: Best mean error results for each category listed in Table 4.

Delay information	Feature	No. Neuron	No. MPCs	k	NNet-t	NNet-g	kNN	W-kNN
Absolute delay	NPF	200	2	3	0.01	0.01	0.75	0.76
Relative delay (no power)	RNPF	200	2	3	6.72	6.77	7.39	6.50
Relative delay (with power)	RNPFp	125	2	3	0.23	0.29	1.25	1.29
No delay	nPAF	200	2	3	0.43	0.56	1.58	1.62

O. ACCURACY-COMPUTATIONAL COMPLEXITY TRADE-OFF

A trade-off exists between localization accuracy and computational complexity among the considered methods. The W-kNN method requires distance calculations to all database fingerprints, resulting in high online complexity for large datasets, whereas the proposed shallow NNet performs only a fixed number of operations yielding lower computational cost after training. Increasing the number of MPCs raises computational load, but using only the strongest two MPCs provides near-optimal NNet accuracy across delay scenarios. In contrast, covariance-based localization relies on high-dimensional channel statistics, leading to substantially higher computational and memory requirements.

P. PRACTICAL DEPLOYMENT CHALLENGES

One of the challenges of implementing super resolution based localization, is to have low complexity algorithms to estimate super resolution feature, especially with absolute delay. Estimation the power-angle super resolution feature is much easier compared to the delay-power-angle super resolution feature [24], [25]. For practical implementation, hardware impairments and synchronization offsets need to be considered [44], [45]. The power-angle feature can be estimated from spatial covariance matrix, which is insensitive to time and frequency offsets. However, phase synchronization of the antennas is needed. In future work, the effects of hardware impairments and synchronization issues will be considered.

VI. CONCLUSIONS

In this paper, we considered angle-delay-power super resolution CSI feature for fingerprint localization. In challenging NLoS propagation conditions, the received signal at the base station from two nearby locations may have a small angle difference but a large delay difference. Considering the Cartesian coordinate (rectangular) CSI feature representation may lead to a large feature distance. To tackle this problem, we treated the angle and delay separately and formulated the normalized polar CSI feature. Mathematical analysis of the defined feature is a future research direction. We have considered three cases based on the availability of the delay information of MPCs; absolute delay, relative delay, and no delay. We have investigated the effect of the number of MPCs and the feature representation on the localization performance. We considered W-kNN as well as neural network based fingerprint localization. Simulation results based on DeepMIMO dataset have showed that 1) with the absolute delay, few centimeters localization accuracy is achieved by the proposed neural network, 2) for the relative delay case, less than 30 cm average error can be achieved, and 3) for no delay information, less than 60 cm average error can be achieved. Simulation results, showed that the gain of neural network compared to W-kNN depends on available delay information. For example for the absolute delay case, the gain is 70 folds, for the relative delay case, the gain is 4 folds and for the no-delay case, the gain is 3 folds. Simulation results have showed that for the relative delay case, including the power has significantly improved the localization performance. We have added a uniform noise to the delay information in order to examine the effect of estimation error on localization performance. The results show that the localization performance is sensitive to the noise in the delay domain for all methods investigated. In future work, it would be interesting to evaluate the localization performance based on measured datasets, where the effect of noise and estimation errors of MPCs are considered. In this paper, we have also investigated a deep neural network which maps the covariance matrix (or its eigenvalues) to the localization. Our results showed that as the data set is small, few thousands of samples, deep neural network did not give comparable performance with super resolution angle-power feature. However, the same data set was enough to achieve remarkable (state-of-the-art) by the proposed shallow NNet whose input is the proposed super resolution CSI features only.

ACKNOWLEDGMENT

We acknowledge the computational resources provided by the Aalto Science-IT project.

APPENDIX

For the sake of brevity and convenience of the reader, we present all the simulation results in the Appendix. The CDF, average, 80th percentile of the errors for different features and algorithms are shown.

REFERENCES

- [1] S. Dwivedi, R. Shreevastav, F. Munier, J. Nygren, I. Siomina, Y. Lyazidi, D. Shrestha, G. Lindmark, P. Ernström, E. Stare, S. M. Razavi, S. Muruganathan, G. Masini, Åke Busin, and F. Gunnarsson, "Positioning in 5G networks," *IEEE Commun. Mag.*, vol. 59, no. 11, pp. 38–44, 2021.
- [2] A. Khafa, J. A. del Peral-Rosado, J. A. Lopez-Salcedo, and G. Seco-Granados, "Evaluation of 5G positioning performance based on UTDaA, AoA and base-station selective exclusion," *Sensors*, vol. 22, no. 1, 2022.
- [3] R. Keating, M. Säily, J. Hulkkonen, and J. Karjalainen, "Overview of positioning in 5G new radio," in *Proc. of IEEE ISWCS*, 2019, pp. 320–324.
- [4] X. Fang, W. Feng, Y. Chen, N. Ge, and Y. Zhang, "Joint communication and sensing toward 6G: Models and potential of using MIMO," *IEEE Internet Things J.*, vol. 10, no. 5, pp. 4093–4116, 2023.
- [5] A. Khafa, J. A. del Peral-Rosado, G. Seco-Granados, and J. A. Lopez-Salcedo, "Performance of NLOS base station exclusion in cmWave 5G positioning," in *Proc. of VTC-Spring*, 2021, pp. 1–5.
- [6] A. Urruela, A. Pages-Zamora, and J. Riba, "Divide-and-conquer based closed-form position estimation for AOA and TDOA measurements," in *Proc. of IEEE ICASSP*, vol. 4, 2006, pp. IV–IV.
- [7] A. Gaber and A. Omar, "A study of wireless indoor positioning based on joint TDOA and DOA estimation using 2-D matrix pencil algorithms and IEEE 802.11ac," *IEEE Trans. Wirel. Commun.*, vol. 14, no. 5, pp. 2440–2454, 2015.
- [8] J. Li, I.-T. Lu, and J. Lu, "Cramer-Rao lower bound analysis of data fusion for fingerprinting localization in non-line-of-sight environments," *IEEE Access*, vol. 9, pp. 18 607–18 624, 2021.
- [9] C. Gentner, T. Jost, W. Wang, S. Zhang, A. Dammann, and U.-C. Fiebig, "Multipath assisted positioning with simultaneous localization and mapping," *IEEE Trans. Wirel. Commun.*, vol. 15, no. 9, pp. 6104–6117, 2016.
- [10] X. Zhu, W. Qu, T. Qiu, L. Zhao, M. Atiquzzaman, and D. O. Wu, "Indoor intelligent fingerprint-based localization: Principles, approaches and challenges," *IEEE Commun. Surveys Tuts.*, vol. 22, no. 4, pp. 2634–2657, 2020.
- [11] E. Gonultas, E. Lei, J. Langerman, H. Huang, and C. Studer, "CSI-Based multi-antenna and multi-point indoor positioning using probability fusion," *IEEE Trans. Wireless Commun.*, vol. 21, no. 4, pp. 2162–2176, 2022.
- [12] X. Sun, X. Gao, G. Y. Li, and W. Han, "Single-site localization based on a new type of fingerprint for massive MIMO-OFDM systems," *IEEE Trans. Veh. Technol.*, vol. 67, no. 7, pp. 6134–6145, 2018.
- [13] A. Sobehy, E. Renault, and P. Muhlethaler, "CSI-MIMO: K-nearest neighbor applied to indoor localization," in *Proc. ICC*, 2020, pp. 1–6.
- [14] X. Li, H. Al-Tous, S. E. Hajri, and O. Tirkkonen, "Channel covariance based fingerprint localization," in *IEEE VTC-fall*, 2024.
- [15] X. Sun, C. Wu, X. Gao, and G. Y. Li, "Fingerprint-based localization for massive MIMO-OFDM system with deep convolutional neural networks," *IEEE Trans. Veh. Technol.*, vol. 68, no. 11, pp. 10 846–10 857, 2019.
- [16] H. Zhang, Z. Wang, W. Xia, Y. Ni, and H. Zhao, "Weighted adaptive KNN algorithm with historical information fusion for fingerprint positioning," *IEEE Wirel Commun Lett*, vol. 11, no. 5, pp. 1002–1006, 2022.
- [17] S. Liu, R. D. Lacerda, and J. Fiorina, "Performance analysis of adaptive k for weighted k-nearest neighbor based indoor positioning," in *Proc. of VTC 2022-Spring*, 2022, pp. 1–5.
- [18] P. Kazemi, H. Al-Tous, T. Ponnada, C. Studer, and O. Tirkkonen, "Beam SNR prediction using channel charting," *IEEE Trans. Veh. Technol.*, pp. 1–16, 2023.
- [19] V. Palhares, S. Taner, and C. Studer, "Csi2vec: Towards a universal csi feature representation for positioning and channel charting," 2025. [Online]. Available: <https://arxiv.org/abs/2506.05237>
- [20] S. Alikhani, G. Charan, and A. Alkhateeb, "LWM: A pre-trained wireless foundation model for universal feature extraction," in *Proc. IEEE ICMLCN*, 2025, pp. 1–6.
- [21] J. Ott, J. Pirkil, M. Stahlke, T. Feigl, and C. Mutschler, "Radio foundation models: Pre-training transformers for 5G-based indoor localization," in *Proc. IPIN*, 2024, pp. 1–6.
- [22] J. Jiang, W. Yu, Y. Li, Y. Gao, and S. Xu, "A MIMO wireless channel foundation model via CIR-CSI consistency," in *Proc. IEEE ICMLCN*, 2025, pp. 1–6.
- [23] G. Pan, K. Huang, H. Chen, S. Zhang, C. Häger, and H. Wymeersch, "Large wireless localization model (lwlm): A foundation model for positioning in 6G networks," 2025. [Online]. Available: <https://arxiv.org/abs/2505.10134>

FIGURE 8: Results of different feature vectors in subsection V-D. (Left): CDF of the errors for the NNet generalization (NNet with 100 neurons). (Middle): Average error for different methods and features. (Right) zoom into the (NPF and SRF) results in the middle figure.

FIGURE 9: Results for different number of neurons in subsection V-E : (Left): CDF of the NNet training errors for different number of neurons. (Middle): CDF of the NNet generalization errors. (Right): Average error.

FIGURE 10: Results for different number of MPCs in subsection V-F. (Left): CDF of the NNet generalization errors for different number of MPCs. (Middle): CDF of the W-kNN generalization errors. (Right): Average error.

FIGURE 11: Results for 3, 5 and 10 nearest neighbors in subsection V-H. (Left): CDF of the W-kNN generalization errors. (Middle): Average error. (Right): 80th percentile of the errors.

FIGURE 12: Relative Delay case, results for the features without power (RNPF) and with power (RNPFp) and for different number of MPCs in subsection V-I. (Left): CDFs of the NNet generalization errors. (Middle): Average error. (Right): 80th percentile of the errors.

FIGURE 13: Relative Delay case, results for different number of neurons in subsection V-J. (Left): CDF of the NNet generalization errors for different number of neurons. (Middle): Average error. (Right): 80th percentile of the errors.

FIGURE 14: Relative Delay case, results for different number of MPCs in subsection V-K. (Left): CDF of the NNet generalization errors for different number of MPCs. (Middle): Average error. (Right): CDF of the W-kNN generalization errors.

FIGURE 15: Relative Delay case, results for different number of nearest neighbors in subsection V-L. (Left): CDF of the W-kNN generalization errors. (Middle): Average error for 3, 5 and 10 nearest neighbors. (Right): 80th percentile of the errors for the kNN and W-kNN.

FIGURE 16: No Delay case, comparison of APF and nPAF, number of neurons is 100. V-M. (Left): CDFs of the NNNet generalization errors. (Middle): 80th percentile of the errors. (Right): Average error.

FIGURE 17: No Delay case, comparison of APF and nPAF, number of neurons is 200. V-M. (Left): CDFs of the NNNet generalization errors. (Middle): 80th percentile of the errors. (Right): Average error.

[24] C.-X. Wang, J. Bian, J. Sun, W. Zhang, and M. Zhang, "A survey of 5G channel measurements and models," *IEEE Commun. Surv. Tutor.*, vol. 20, no. 4, pp. 3142–3168, 2018.

[25] H. Xu, Y. Zhang, B. Ba, D. Wang, and X. Li, "Fast joint estimation of time of arrival and angle of arrival in complex multipath environment using OFDM," *IEEE Access*, vol. 6, pp. 60 613–60 621, 2018.

[26] Y. Hua, "Estimating two-dimensional frequencies by matrix enhancement and matrix pencil," *IEEE Trans Signal Process*, vol. 40, no. 9, pp. 2267–2280, 1992.

[27] A.-J. vanderVeen, M. Vanderveen, and A. Paulraj, "Joint angle and delay estimation using shift-invariance techniques," *IEEE Trans Signal Process*, vol. 46, no. 2, pp. 405–418, 1998.

[28] Z. Li, A. Nimr, P. Schulz, and G. Fettweis, "Enhanced superresolution path delay estimation for channel impulse response based localization," in *Proc. of IEEE (ICC Workshops)*, 2024, pp. 697–702.

[29] J. Bi, M. Zhao, G. Zheng, T. Chen, H. Cao, G. Yao, F. Su, T. Wang, W. Li, and G. Zhang, "Exploiting high-precision AoA estimation method using CSI from a single WiFi station," *Signal Processing*, vol. 228, p. 109750, 2025.

[30] M. Triki, D. T. M. Slock, V. Rigal, and P. Francois, "Mobile terminal positioning via power delay profile fingerprinting: Reproducible validation simulations," in *Proc. of IEEE VTC*, 2006, pp. 1–5.

[31] A. Kirmaz, T. Sahin, D. S. Michalopoulos, and W. Gerstacker, "Time-based vs. fingerprinting-based positioning using artificial neural networks," in *Proc. of IPIN*, 2023, pp. 1–6.

[32] D. Slock, "Diversity aspects of power delay profile based location fingerprinting," in *Proc. IEEE ICASSP*, 2012, pp. 2861–2864.

[33] S. Liu, L. Tang, and Z. Wang, "Fingerprint localization based on hybrid TOA, AOA, and RSS measurements," *Discov Appl Sci*, vol. 7, no. 93, pp. 1–9, 2025.

[34] C. Studer, S. Medjkouh, E. Gonultaş, T. Goldstein, and O. Tirkkonen, "Channel charting: Locating users within the radio environment using channel state information," *IEEE Access*, vol. 6, pp. 47 682–47 698, 2018.

[35] J. Deng, S. Medjkouh, N. Malm, O. Tirkkonen, and C. Studer, "Multipoint channel charting for wireless networks," in *Proc. Asilomar Conf. Sign., Syst., Comput.*, Oct. 2018, pp. 286–290.

[36] H. AL-Tous, P. Kazemi, C. Studer, and O. Tirkkonen, "Channel charting with angle-delay-power-profile features and earth-mover distance," in *Proc. of Asilomar Conf. Sign., Syst., Comput.*, 2022, pp. 1195–1201.

[37] Z. Uykan, H. Al-Tous, Y. Ali, R. Jäntti, and O. Tirkkonen, "Angle-delay features and distances for channel charting," in *Proc. of IEEE WCNC 2024*, 2024.

[38] B. Fleury, M. Tschudin, R. Heddergott, D. Dahlhaus, and K. I. Pedersen, "Channel parameter estimation in mobile radio environments using the SAGE algorithm," *IEEE J. Sel. Areas Commun.*, vol. 17, no. 3, pp. 434–450, 1999.

[39] M. Steinbauer et.al, "How to quantify multipath separation," *IEEE Trans. Electron*, vol. E82, pp. 1–5, 1999.

[40] N. Czink, P. Cera, J. Salo, E. Bonek, J. pekka Nuutinen, and J. Ylitalo, "A framework for automatic clustering of parametric MIMO channel data including path powers," in *Proc. of IEEE VTC*, 2006, pp. 1–5.

[41] S. Arora and B. Barak, *Computational complexity: a modern approach*. Cambridge University Press, 2009.

[42] A. Alkhateeb, "DeepMIMO: A generic deep learning dataset for millimeter wave and massive MIMO applications," in *Proc. ITA*, Feb. 2019, pp. 1–8.

[43] Remcom, "Wireless InSite," <http://www.remcom.com/wireless-insite>.

[44] H. Chen, M. F. Keskin, S. R. Aghdam, H. Kim, S. Lindberg, A. Wolfgang, T. E. Abruđan, T. Eriksson, and H. Wymeersch, "Modeling and analysis of OFDM-based 5G/6G localization under hardware impairments," *IEEE Trans. Wirel. Commun.*, pp. 1–1, 2023.

[45] D. Zhang, D. Wu, K. Niu, X. Wang, F. Zhang, J. Yao, D. Jiang, and F. Qin, "Practical issues and challenges in CSI-based Integrated sensing and communication," in *Proc. of IEEE (ICC Workshops)*, 2022, pp. 836–841.

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